

ANALYSIS OF THE FLORA OF HISAR STATE RESERVE BY LIFE FORMS

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Abstract. In this work, the analysis of the species distributed in the flora of Hisar State Reserve by life forms is presented. The analysis of species in the flora was carried out based on the classification developed by S.Raunkiaer. According to this, it was known that hemicryptophytes, characteristic of Mountainous Central Asia, took the leading place in the flora by the number of species, followed by therophytes, cryptophytes, phanerophytes and chamephytes.

Keywords. Reserve, family, genus, species, mountainous Central Asia, chamephyte, phanerophyte, cryptophyte, therophyte, hemicryptophyte.

Hisar state reserve was established in 1983 as a result of merging two independent reserves of Miraki and Kyzilsuv in Kashkadarya region based on the decision No. 521 of the former Council of Ministers of Uzbekistan dated 09.09.83 [5]. It was established in order to preserve the natural complexes in the south-eastern part of the Hisar mountain ranges, to study their natural processes, and to preserve the gene pool of representatives of flora and fauna that are in danger of disappearing in this area [13]. The total land area of the reserve is 78,986.1 [10] (2000 ha. reserve zone was issued) hectares. The region consists of 4 divisions: Gilan, Miraki, Tankhozdarya and Kyzilsuv. For the first time, the species composition of the flora of the reserve was clarified based on the materials collected from the field research and the samples stored in herbarium funds. According to this, it became known that 71 families, 1298 species belonging to 457 genera are distributed in the flora of the reserve. Flowering plants are the main part of them, open-seeded plants are few in number, although they are numerous. The biological spectrum of life forms in the flora is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Biological spectrum of the composition of the flora of Hisar state reserve
(S. Raunkiaer, 1934 year)

Taxon		Life forms					
		Phanerophyte	Khamefit	Hemicryptophyte	Cryptophyte	Therophyte	Total
PHYLUM	CLASS						
Lycophytes	Equisetidae				2		2
	Polypodiidae			3			3
Pinidae	Pinales						
Gnetidae	Ephedrales	6					6
Magnoliids	Dicotyledones	79	65	562	28	343	1069
	Monocotyledones			91	81	46	218
Total :		79	65	656	109	389	1298
Percentage (%) indicators		6,0 9	5	50, 5	8,39	29,9 6	100

The analysis of life forms was carried out according to the classification developed by S. Raunkiaer (1934) [1]. Hemicryptophytes dominate the species count, followed by therophytes, cryptophytes, phanerophytes, and chamephytes (Figure 1). Figure 1 shows the taxonomic status of life forms.

According to the number of species, it belonged to chamephytes with at least 65 species. Chamephytes are perennial plants consisting of semi-shrubs. There are

4 types in the classification developed by S. Raunkiaer [1]: Suffruticose chamaephytes, Passive chamaephytes, Active chamaephytes and Cushion chamaephytes [1]. We perform the analysis in the general hamefit style. The flora includes 12 families, 65 chamaephytes belonging to 26 genera, 5% of the total species. The distribution of all chamaephytes in the flora is limited to the province of Mountainous Central Asia. In conclusion, the main part of the species corresponded to the species of Acantholimon, Astragalus, Artemisia, Scutellaria, and these species form the basis of the plant community in the upland region of the reserve flora.

Phanerophytes occupy the largest number of species with 79 species. According to the classification of species in this category, consisting of trees and shrubs, they are divided into nano, micro, meso, mego phanerophytes [1]. The phanerophyte species distributed in the flora were accepted according to the general phanerophytes, this situation was used in most floristic studies conducted in Uzbekistan [6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12]. According to the taxonomic status of phanerophytes in the flora, there are 79 species belonging to 18 families, 29 genera, and they make up 6.08% of the flora.

The main part of cryptophyte species is the species belonging to the families Orchidaceae, Asphodelaceae, Iridaceae, Liliaceae and Amaryllidaceae belonging to the ancestor of Monocotyledones. The remaining species belong to the representatives of Apiaceae, Papaveraceae, Berberidaceae Ranunculaceae, Berberidaceae from the ancestor of Dicotyledones. Cryptophytic species belong to 15 families, 32 genera and 109 species and make up 8.39% of the flora.

Therophytes are next in number of hemicrypophytes. In the flora of the region, 34 families, 389 species belonging to 203 families belong to this type. These species make up 29.96% of the total flora. The families Boraginaceae, Caryophyllaceae, Fabaceae, Poaceae, Brassicaceae, Asteraceae with more than 18 species of therophytes in the flora amount to 250 species, and these correspond to 64.26% of therophytes in the total flora. The number of species in families such as Juncaceae, Cannabaceae, Urticaceae, Violaceae, Thymelaeaceae, Resedaceae, Portulacaceae, Balsaminaceae, Primulaceae, Mazaceae is 1. On average, 1 family has 11.44 species.

In all the floristic studies conducted on the local flora of mountainous Central Asia, it was observed that hemicryptophytes dominate [2, 3, 4, 6, 7]. Similarly, hemicryptophytes dominated in the study area. 656 hemicryptophytes belonging to 43 families, 239 genera were registered in the flora, which is 50.53% of the total species in the flora. Apiaceae (20/41), Lamiaceae (14/45),

Poaceae (28/67), Fabaceae (18/109), Asteraceae (45/128) have a large number of species. After these, there are families such as Boraginaceae (10/16), Cyperaceae (8/21), Rosaceae (7/23), Caryophyllaceae (8/23), Ranunculaceae (11/34). Papaveraceae, Berberidaceae, Saxifragaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Datisceae, Celastraceae, Biebersteiniaceae Nitrariaceae with 1 species each, all with a hemicryptophytic life form. There are families with 1 to 128 species in number of species. Average 1 family has 15.25 species. Hemicryptophyta belongs to the families in which most of the species are polymorphic.

In conclusion, according to the results of the biomorphological analysis of the flora of the reserve, the abundance of hemicryptophyte species distributed in the flora indicates that the entire mountain belongs to the mountain flora of Central Asia. Therophytes, followed by hemicryptophytes, are the main species of the Holarctic, Palearctic and Ancient Mediterranean, with a distribution from the plains to the high mountain region. In the flora, phanerophytes make up the main part of the plant communities, and in comparison with other reserve and local flora, the number of species is greater, this situation depends on the location of the area (connection with the water environment, that is, the abundance of streams and rivers), while most of them do not go beyond the mountainous Central Asia. corresponds to species. The distribution of all chamephytes in the flora is limited to the Mountainous Central Asian, and the main part is the species of the families Acantholimon, Astragalus, Artemisia, Scutellaria, and these species form the basis of the plant community in the highland region of the flora of the reserve. Cryptophytes are as unique as other regions in Central Asia, but the gene pool of ornamental species is well preserved due to the protection of the area and its remoteness from inhabited areas.

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